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*Examining the Role of the Air Cargo in
Enhancing Italy's Economic Development
and Resilience*

Examining the Role of the Air Cargo in Enhancing Italy's Economic Development and Resilience

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Abstract

This study focuses on the strategic importance of the air cargo sector, highlighting its crucial role in supporting economic development and resilience in the face of global challenges. Despite its relatively modest share of overall freight traffic, air cargo stands out for its significant contribution to the value of Italy's international trade. Through an analysis that includes the evaluation of transportation modal shares, trade balances, and categories of goods transported, we highlight air cargo's strategic importance for an export-oriented economy and its ability to overcome national logistical and infrastructure limitations. In particular, the analysis compares the Italian air cargo sector with those of other major European countries, revealing a delay in development that cannot be attributed solely to demand factors. The lack of a prominent national air cargo carrier emerges as a critical factor, suggesting the need for strategic initiatives to strengthen Italy's air cargo strategy given that synergies in aggregation processes may lead to business opportunities. Our study also offers policy recommendations to address the strategic challenges identified and improve operational efficiency and market adaptability. We highlight the need for policies that overcome current limitations and capitalize on future growth opportunities to strengthen a country's or region's competitive position in a global landscape.

Introduction

Global growth has remained fragile recently because of successive crises, with international trade slowing because of increasing protectionism, particularly through nontariff barriers. To stimulate growth, policymakers have focused on macroeconomic policies. In the current context, it is important to focus on structural issues related to business productivity and countries' competitiveness. Production delocalization pushed over the past two decades has now shown distortions in product, labor, skills, and infrastructure markets that must be properly addressed to avoid

competitiveness drifts. Economic openness through international trade and investment is essential for economic development and global stability.

In recent years, global trade has been highly volatile, intensified by rising geopolitical tensions that threaten to further fragment markets and reduce international cooperation. In the context of economic uncertainty, the role of strategic sectors is crucial for economic resilience. Air cargo has a significant impact on a country's economy, facilitating the expansion of foreign trade, export diversification, and the attraction of foreign direct investment. In parallel, adequate infrastructure, particularly those related to intermodal aspects, is the mainstay of the sector's efficiency, enabling optimized logistics through the ability to move large volumes of cargo and integrate with other means of transportation.

Transportation plays a key role in international trade, serving as a vital link between global markets. The ability to move goods quickly and efficiently is essential to ensure that trade flows remain fluid, even in an environment of increasing geopolitical complexity and fragmented supply chains. Logistics, through integrated transportation management, enables goods to reach global markets in competitive time, reducing costs and risks associated with delays or disruptions by facilitating participation in international trade and access to new markets. Within this framework, the strategic role of air cargo transportation is considered.

Despite its modest share of overall cargo traffic, the contribution of air cargo is remarkable. This study investigates the role of this industry in today's modern integrated economies. A pivotal section of the analysis compares Italy's air cargo sector with those of other major European countries, revealing a lag in development that cannot be attributed solely to demand-driven factors. The consequences of a national carrier with an inadequate market share and its implications for Italy's air cargo capacity and international competitiveness are critically assessed, offering a comprehensive overview of the associated challenges and opportunities.

Three research questions (RQs) prompted this study. Using RQ1, we examine the role of air cargo in the economic openness. RQ2 investigates the positioning of the Italian air cargo sector from a European perspective using RQ2. Finally, RQ3 addresses the strategic challenges and opportunities for the industry.

In this context, we argue that public policies should be geared toward supply chain resilience and sustainability to mitigate the risks of global economic crises. Thus, there is a need to strengthen international collaboration and invest in critical infrastructure, such as that related to air cargo, to ensure the continuity and efficiency of trade flows. Policy planning should also focus on technological innovation, the integration of advanced logistics systems, and the adoption of circular economic practices to increase global value chain resilience.

Our analysis highlights the essential role of air cargo in the economy and calls for strategic initiatives to bolster its growth to increase a country's or region's resilience and competitive position in the global market. By examining statistical data, trends, and comparative analyses, we seek to provide a deep understanding of the air cargo sector's current landscape and potential trajectory. Policymakers' planning efforts should include strategies to diversify supply sources to reduce dependence on individual markets and minimize the impact of future crises. Creating secure trade corridors, supporting multilateral trade initiatives, and promoting greater transparency in international supply chains can contribute to a more resilient global trading system that is less susceptible to geopolitical fluctuations.

Background

International trade plays a crucial role in enhancing countries' competitiveness, and their relationship is complex and embraces multiple economic, technological, political, and risk dimensions. An increase in trade intensity is positively correlated with improved competitiveness [x] because it stimulates greater interdependence. Competitiveness can be assessed using various trade-based indices that provide a detailed view of a country's performance in global markets [y], and several studies have confirmed this approach [z]. The interconnectedness of trade networks is a crucial factor in understanding competitiveness. The international trade relations of companies' home countries significantly influence their industrial competitiveness [q]. The intertwining of relationships promotes a cooperative environment in which countries can exploit their competitive advantages and reduce weaknesses through trade agreements and strategic partnerships. The influence of international trade on economic growth also emerges in the context of foreign direct investment [w]. This connection underscores the importance of countries actively participating in global trade to attract investment and improve economic performance. Global trade has been characterized by considerable volatility since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, and economic and noneconomic disruptions have had significant effects on global trade since early 2020. Fragmentation and increased heterogeneity also characterize the recent slowdown in global trade. While it is premature to say whether this trend represents a material and long-lasting deviation from established trends, it seems possible that the disruptions caused by the pandemic have triggered a significant shift in global trade that is now fueled by geopolitical issues and risk mitigation strategies. The convergence of these factors raises the possibility that global trade patterns will undergo even more significant changes, ushering in a new era of distinct challenges and opportunities for economies around the world.

Figure 1 - Import and export shares of GDP

Source: Own elaboration, based on UNCT trade data.

Note: Import and export propensities are computed as the value of imports or exports divided by current GDP. Import propensity expresses the proportion of income spent on imports. Export propensity reflects the overall reliance of domestic producers on foreign markets. Higher values imply greater dependence on foreign demand.

On the basis of these macro trends, Table 1 shows the relationships between global GDP (GDP), the quantity of goods transported via air cargo (traffic_q), the value of goods transported via air cargo (traffic_v), the global population (pop) and average global inflation (inf_rate).

Table 1. Correlations among macro variables

	GDP	Traffic_q	Traffic_v	pop	inf_rate
GDP	1				
traffic_q	0.9326	1			
traffic_v	0.8559	0.7707	1		
pop	0.9801	0.9513	0.8298	1	
inf_rate	0.2606	0.0925	0.5748	0.1717	1

Source: own elaboration

The reference variable in this analysis is GDP. There is a strong positive correlation between global GDP and the quantity of goods transported via air cargo (0.9326), suggesting that when the world economy

grows, the volume of goods transported by air also tends to grow. The correlation between GDP and the value of goods transported by air (0.8559) is also very high, although not as strong as the correlation between GDP and quantity. The correlation between the quantity and value of air cargo is also strongly positive (0.7707), indicating that the value of the goods transported increases when the quantity of goods transported increases. However, the relationship between inflation and goods transported is less straightforward: a correlation of 0.5748 shows that there is a moderately positive relationship between the value of goods transported and inflation, whereas the correlation between inflation and quantity is weak (0.0925), suggesting that the volume of goods transported is not strongly related to the inflation rate. Another interpretation here is that when inflation is increasing, customers restrict purchases but that inflation increases the value of goods shipped even if the quantity is unchanged.

In 2022, each of the top ten airports for cargo handling globally handled an average of 3.16 million tons of cargo. Hong Kong Airport (HKG) was the busiest, with 4.20 million tons handled, followed by Memphis (MEM), with 4.04 million, and Anchorage (ANC), with 3.46 million. Other significant global hubs include Shanghai (PVG), Louisville (SDF), Incheon (ICN), Taipei (TPE), Los Angeles (LAX), Tokyo (NRT), and Doha (DOH). In contrast, major cargo airports in Europe handled an average of just 1.36 million tons, with no European airport in the top ten globally. The largest cargo hub in Europe is Frankfurt (FRA), at 1.97 million tons, followed by Charles de Gaulle (CDG) in Paris, with 1.89 million tons, and Leipzig/Halle (LEJ), with 1.51 million tons. Other European airports on the list include Amsterdam Schiphol (AMS), Istanbul (IST), London Heathrow (LHR), Liège (LGG), Luxembourg (LUX), Cologne/Bonn (CGN), and Milan Malpensa (MPX).

Given the difference in the average volume of goods handled by non-European versus European hubs, it would be strategic for Europe to invest in expanding and improving its air cargo infrastructure. This would allow Europe to strengthen its role in global trade and potentially stimulate the continent's economic growth. Indeed, expanding the air cargo infrastructure may increase employment in other areas but could also have negative externalities in specific territories, whereas positive externalities emerge in others.

The air cargo industry plays a key role in global trade and significantly impacts the dynamics of international trade [1]. Despite accounting for less than 1% of the total volume of global cargo traffic, air cargo accounts for approximately one-third of trade in terms of value [2], [3]. Not surprisingly, countries with favorable air cargo policies are more competitive in this field [4]. International trade flows are crucial to economic development [5], and as is commonly recognized, competition for air cargo is influenced by factors such as demand variation, sustainability and service quality [6], [7], [8].

This industry is essential to the global economy because it facilitates international trade that supports economic growth, particularly because of its significant contribution to moving high-value goods and to the overall balance of trade [10]. The sector's strategic importance is further underscored by its role in connecting regional centers of production and consumption [10], [11]. Air cargo plays a substantial role in improving the efficiency and responsiveness of modern supply chains [12]. It is essential for businesses at the local level and serves as a key driver of economic growth and development [10]. The industry's resilience and adaptability are evident during difficult periods; for example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, air cargo emerged as a new opportunity for the aviation sector [13]. In addition, the importance of increasing sustainability efforts has emerged as prominent, with countries increasingly focusing on improving logistics sustainability [14], [15]. This adds up to core business

activities like forecasting demand, providing quality service within cargo terminals, in a competitive environment [16]. Managing air cargo operations efficiently at airports and responding to industry-specific challenges are key to meeting market demands [17], and technological advances provide innovative solutions to logistics challenges in air cargo [18].

Air cargo infrastructure is crucial in logistics networks because it enhances trade and economic development. A region's logistics infrastructure, including its air cargo facilities, is essential for improving trade flows and connectivity [19]. The efficiency of an air cargo infrastructure directly affects trade networks, as it influences the drivers of international trade [20]. Regional airports also benefit from air cargo services and road connectivity, highlighting the importance of air cargo in supporting regional hub development [22]. Therefore, regional airports must carefully examine their development plans to meet upcoming challenges and improve their competitiveness [42].

The interaction between infrastructure and logistics networks in facilitating trade, optimizing supply chains, and developing regional economies is clear. An adequate infrastructure contributes to the efficiency of logistics operations, improves connectivity, and supports the growth of businesses reliant on timely and reliable freight transportation. Integrating various modes of transportation, including air, rail, sea, and road, allows goods to move smoothly, helps optimize supply chain operations, and reduces logistics costs [23], [24]. Intermodal transportation systems facilitate coordination among different transportation modes, promoting rapid information flows, interoperability, and efficient operations [25]. This integration helps reduce external costs related to air pollution, congestion, and accidents, thus promoting transportation sustainability [26].

Intermodal optimization between air and high-speed rail transport has helped to optimize routes and increase connectivity, benefiting both sectors [28]. Efficiency in intermodal transport is closely linked to factors such as terminal layout, terminal resource management, and the use of digital technologies to optimize port operations [29], [30]. Such intermodal integration facilitates smooth cargo transfer, minimizes waiting times and maximizes logistical efficiency, all of which are crucial to maintaining and improving an area's competitiveness internationally [31].

The air cargo industry faces several challenges that have been exacerbated by global events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and infrastructure limitations. The pandemic has significantly impacted the global aviation industry, creating challenges such as border closures, restrictive travel measures, and a reduction in the demand for air travel [33], [34]. These disruptions have affected millions of air transport users and stakeholders, highlighting the air cargo industry's vulnerability to unforeseen global events [35].

In addition, infrastructure constraints pose significant challenges to the air cargo sector. Airport capacity constraints, obsolete cargo handling facilities, and inadequate intermodal connectivity hinder efficiency and operational capacity [37], [38]. The complexity of palletizing in the air cargo industry and aviation security regulations poses significant operational challenges [38]. In addition, unstable macroeconomic conditions can cause fluctuations in the supply of and demand for goods, affecting the air cargo trade and increasing decision-making challenges for industry stakeholders [39].

Air cargo significantly improves supply chain resilience and adaptability to global market changes [43]. The speed and efficiency of air cargo help supply chains respond promptly to market fluctuations and disruptions, thereby improving their overall adaptability [43], [44]. The ability of air cargo to quickly

connect distant markets improves the flexibility and responsiveness of global supply chains to changing market demands [45].

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the importance of air transport in serving global supply chains by offering integrated and efficient delivery services even during massive disruptions [43]. Strategies implemented by China's air cargo sector in response to the pandemic aimed to increase air cargo capacity to improve the safety and resilience of its industries and supply chains [46]. Adaptability among air cargo suppliers is essential for the continuity of supply chain operations [47].

In addition, collaboration among stakeholders across air cargo supply chains improves the resilience and competitiveness of such chains [48]. The strategic positioning of air cargo within modern supply chains underscores its significant role in ensuring supply chain efficiency and adaptability to market changes [49].

Research design and questions.

We employ a desk research strategy in this study. This approach is useful for systematically analyzing various data sources, including academic literature, industry reports, and statistical publications. Our analytical process involves reviewing existing academic work, quantitative data analysis, and comparative studies to construct a nuanced understanding of this industry's economic contributions, logistics dynamics, and international trade implications.

Desk research facilitates the triangulation of data, improving the robustness of separate findings by confirming information from different databases and reports. This secondary data analysis allows us to construct a comprehensive overview of the evolution of the air cargo sector, its strategic importance in the balance of trade, and how its operations are concentrated globally and within specific regional contexts.

Our research questions (RQs) supported our investigation; specifically, we address temporal trends in the modal share and value of air cargo, the sector's contribution to trade surpluses, its strategic positioning relative to regional and international market dynamics, and the overall challenges and prospects for the sector's growth. By correlating this research approach with these investigations, we broaden the academic discourse on air cargo logistics and propose strategic insights for strengthening competitive advantages in the global air cargo sector.

Adopting a desk research methodology allows us to explore specific RQs with rigor and methodological precision. This approach upholds the validity and reliability of the research findings and contributes to a broader understanding of the air cargo industry's strategic levers.

Research questions.

In light of the complex dynamics and strategic role of air cargo in the Italian economy, this study is based on RQs designed to clarify this sector's impact, challenges, and future prospects. It is important to understand how air cargo transport contributes to the economy in terms of added value and the specific characteristics that make it indispensable for international trade.

We investigate the role of air cargo transport in trade balance: RQ1: How does air cargo impact trade balance, and which categories of goods are most dependent on air cargo?

Also, we investigate the competitive positioning of the Italian air cargo sector from a European and global perspective by asking RQ2: How does Italy compare to other major economies in terms of air cargo volume, infrastructure, and carrier capacity?

Finally, we delve into the strategic challenges and opportunities facing the sector with RQ3: What are the main barriers to growth and efficiency, and what strategic initiatives could improve the competitiveness of the air cargo market?

Evidence

Focusing on prominent European markets, Figure Y illustrates traffic trends over the past decade. From a volume perspective, divergent trends emerge. However, from a production and allocative perspective, several strategic insights are noteworthy. The largest cargo airport also serves as the main hub for the national carrier, enabling synergies between cargo and passenger transport. In contrast, much of Italy’s air cargo is handled in Milan, while the national carrier’s hub is in Rome, see Figure Z for traffic details. With limited long-haul passenger flights, Milan Malpensa relies more on dedicated cargo flights than belly cargo, and many global destinations lack direct connections to Milan. This leads to inefficiencies in the allocation of production factors and increased costs. A significant volume of Italian goods is transported by road to Frankfurt airport before being shipped by air.

Figure Y - Cargo trends in Italy and major countries (Indices 2004=100)

Source: Elaborations on Enac data, Traffic Data 2023 and previous years. See annex 1 for quantities

Italy ranks sixth in the volume of goods moved compared with major European countries. However, it ranks second in terms of manufacturing value added and fourth in overall GDP. For air cargo, Germany is the top-ranked country, with 4.6 million tons in 2023, followed by France, with 2.4 million tons; Belgium, with 1.7 million tons; the Netherlands, with 1.5 million tons; Italy, with 1.1 million tons; Spain,

which is expected to have reached almost 1 million tons in 2023; and Luxembourg, with 0.8 million tons.

The lack of a major national carrier has hindered cargo development

Air cargo is less developed in Italy than in other major EU economies, a condition that limits the country's economic openness to global markets. In other major EU markets, major national carriers offer high cargo capacity, which is partly achieved through large-capacity cargo-only aircraft but mainly through the joint transport of passengers and cargo on long-haul scheduled flights.

Figure 13 - Air cargo of main EU countries and carriers (2019), millions of tons

Country	Country	Carrier	Countries	Share
DE-AU-CH	Lufthansa	1.4	5.4	25.9%
FR-ND	AF-Klm	1.1	4.1	26.8%
UK	British Airways	0.5	2.6	19.2%
ES	Iberia	0.2	0.8	25.0%
IT	Alitalia	0.1	1.1	9.1%

Source: Elaborations on Eurostat and air carrier data.

The 0.2 million tons of cargo foregone due to Italy's low growth rate compared with other EU countries since 2008, would be the same as the volume foregone by the domestic carrier compared with its foreign counterparts. The newly privatized Alitalia took off in 2009, and the airline's new management gave up the cargo fleet and drastically cut back on long-haul flights, which capture the greatest share of cargo shipped by airplanes.

Figure 14 - Air cargo of European flag carriers (kg of cargo carried per passenger)

EU	3.7	1
North Africa	10.7	7.5
Middle East	25.6	13.8
North America	32	13.7
Asia	47.9	33.3
Other Long haul	25.7	16.4

Source: Elaborations on data from the Association of European Airlines (2015)

Business case

This section presents key evidence which can serve as a representative case study given a country's degree of trade openness. Air cargo represents a seemingly marginal mode of transportation because the limited quantities transported result in a very small modal share. However, it is the most suitable means of transport for high and very high value-added types of goods, urgent deliveries, and goods that must travel over long distances. The combination of these three characteristics can make air cargo attractive and competitive with other modes. In terms of volume, air cargo accounts for approximately 0.2% of all cargo traffic, but in terms of value, its share is close to 10%. In 2022, Italy exported 670 million tons of goods worth 75 billion euros and imported 320 million tons of goods worth 44 billion euros.

	Air	Railways	Pipeline	Road	Ship
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Volume	0.21	10.1	7	28	54
Value	9.41	13.9	5	39	53

Figure 3 - Modal shares of Italy's international transport, in %

Source: Elaborations on Bank of Italy data, Survey of International Freight Transport, 2023.

The surplus balance for the air cargo mode was €31 billion, increasing from €23 billion in 2019, the last pre-pandemic year. In that year, however, the modal share of the value of air transport was 10%. Since 2021, a significant increase in the prices of imported energy goods has contributed to the increase in the value of the modal shares of transportation that the sector uses, mainly shipping and pipeline transport.

Italy's trade surplus, which travels mainly by air and roads, reached €43 billion in 2022, down from €50 in the previous year. Not surprisingly, Italy's trade surplus with the rest of Europe mainly occurs through road transport, whereas the surplus with the rest of the world is from air transport, although it declined from 2021–2022 due to high energy prices. Negative contributions to Italy's trade balance come from rail transport (- €8 billion in 2022), maritime (- €41 billion) and oil and gas pipelines (-€64 billion), the last two worsening sharply because of sharp increases in the prices of energy commodities.

A recent study by Italy's Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport revealed positive balances in the air cargo trade across all the world regions. Therefore, Italy's strong trade openness appears to be able to overcome national transport, logistical, and infrastructural limitations, as well as the absence of a market-dominant national carrier, which has been a success factor in other major European countries, particularly for long-haul businesses.

Figure 5 - Air exports and imports by geographical region (2019, million euros)

	import	Export
Europe	6400	10800
Asia	13000	21000
Middle-east	200	4200
America	10800	18400
Africa	550	700
Other	200	2000

Source: Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, 2020.

East Asia is the main market for air cargo, both as an origin and a destination, with €18.9 billion in exports in 2019 and €11.7 billion in imports, for a positive air cargo trade balance of €7.2 billion. The second-largest market was North America, with a positive air cargo trade balance of more than €6.1 billion. The European Union was the third-largest market in total air trade, with a trade balance of €3.2 billion; however, this balance was less than the positive trade balance in the Middle East of €3.9 billion resulting from the size of that region's exports. In terms of commodity categories, several products, including energy products, minerals, and raw materials, are not suitable for air transport.

Machinery and mechanical equipment are the most important in terms of weight transported in exports and imports, with a total weight close to one-third of the total. The second-largest group includes textiles, clothing, and leather products, which are typically made in Italy but are also present

in the country's imports, with an overall weight of 18%. The third largest, at 15%, are chemical products, within which pharmaceuticals play a key role. This is followed by agri-food products and metals and manufactured products at approximately 10%. The major categories were transportation equipment (8%) and wood and furniture (5%). Interestingly, all of these categories are present in exports and imports in similar percentages; however, exports by volume are more than double the amount of imports, highlighting a probable trade surplus for each of them.

Figure 6 - Composition of air cargo in % (2022), calculated in tons

Material	Export	Import	Total
Other	0.5	3.7	2.89
Transport equipment	10	4.5	7.41
Machineries	29.3	35.7	31.8
Metals	11.9	7.9	10
Chemicals	13.5	16.9	15.4
Wood and furniture	6.45	5	5
Textile	17.45	17.2	17.5
agri-food	10.9	9.1	10

Source: Elaborations on Istat-Ice Statistical Yearbook data on foreign trade, 2023.

The regions of the destinations/origins of air cargo.

Over 90% of Italy's air cargo travels via international routes. Half of that is realized on routes within Europe, with intra-EU routes accounting for approximately 35%, and extra-EU routes accounting for an additional 9%. The intercontinental air cargo trade to and from Italy consists of 15% medium-haul routes to the Middle East and 31% long-haul routes, which are dominated almost equally by Asia and North America. Trade with Central and South America and Africa is limited.

Compared with the pre-COVID-19 period, Italy's air cargo in 2022 grew significantly in several segments: +33% domestic cargo, +16% to the EU, and +20% to North America. However, flows to other regions in 2022 were even lower than those in 2019: -14% to extra-EU European countries, -12% to the Middle East, -19% to Asia, -39% to Central and South America, and -10% to Africa.

Figure 8 - Air cargo by region of destination/origin (thousands of tons)

Origin/Destination	2019	2022
EU	402.6	479.8
Europe	117	100.6
Middle East	183.6	161.6
Asia	193.1	156.4
North America	125	150
South America	22.5	13.7
Africa	15.4	13.9

Source: Elaborations on Enac data, Traffic Data, 2022.

As shown in Figure Z Milan MXP handles two third of Italian market and adding up Rome FCO) airport, the share reaches approximately 80%.

Figure Z - Cargo by airport of origin/destination (thousands of tons)

Airport	Q	Share
Milan	730	65.77%
Rome	155	13.96%
Other	225	20.27%
Total	1110	100%

Source: Elaborations on Enac data, Traffic Data 2023.

Discussion

Trade-related competitiveness depends on several factors. First, policies and regulations must ensure stable macroeconomic conditions and competitive markets. Second, efficient institutions that ensure effective governance, efficient decisions and respect for property rights. Physical infrastructure along with social and knowledge capital that increases investment productivity. Regarding the role of hubs, with cities generating 80% of the world's GDP, local and urban competitiveness is becoming increasingly important.

Here, we contextualize our findings with the literature on the role of air cargo, emphasizing its importance for the Italian economy. The evolution of air cargo's market share underscores a dichotomy: its modest volume contrasts with its substantial contribution in terms of the value of goods shipped [7]. This observation aligns with the literature that characterizes air cargo as a catalyst for economic development, facilitating the rapid movement of high-value, time-sensitive goods across global markets [3], [4]. Our findings are consistent with studies suggesting that despite the small volume of air cargo, its strategic importance in international trade is increasing, helping economies maintain competitive advantages in global markets [22].

Our analysis highlights the significant role of air cargo trade balances, particularly through high-value items such as machinery, pharmaceuticals, and luxury goods, which lead to considerable trade surpluses [9]. This finding is consistent with the literature emphasizing the contribution of air cargo to export-driven economic models, where speed and reliability are paramount [6]. The positive trade balances across various high-value categories underline the fact that the advantages of air transport outweigh its logistical and infrastructure limitations, confirming its crucial role in enhancing competitiveness [8].

The concentration of Italy's air cargo activity in a small number of airports, with Milan Malpensa at the forefront, presents opportunities and challenges [23]. This centralization impacts logistics and distribution strategies, reflecting findings in the literature on the importance of a robust air cargo infrastructure in boosting trade efficiency and regional development [24]. The strategic positioning of airports as hubs for air cargo underscores the need for targeted investment in infrastructure to sustain growth and improve logistics networks, echoing calls from the literature for enhanced intermodal connectivity and infrastructure development [25]. In sum, investments in airport infrastructure, innovative technologies, and intermodal transportation development strategies prove indispensable for building a more resilient economy.

Analyzing Italy's position within the European air cargo sector highlights a lag in the country's development, partly due to the absence of a major national carrier [11]. This finding is critical, as the literature clearly links a national carrier's capacity to the country's competitiveness in terms of air cargo

[12]. The strategic role of carriers in facilitating international connectivity and supporting air cargo capacity is crucial, suggesting a need for policies that bolster carrier operations and expand the global reach [13].

The strategic challenges identified here, notably the lack of major national carrier and infrastructural constraints, echo global concerns about the air cargo sector's resilience to economic and geopolitical shifts [14]. The literature suggests that addressing these challenges through strategic policies and investments in technology, infrastructure, and carrier capacity is vital to enhancing operational efficiency and market adaptability [15]. Our findings advocate for a concerted effort to strengthen Italy's air cargo sector, aligning with global trends toward improving supply chain resilience and sustainability [16].

Our findings, contextualized within the broader literature, highlight the need for strategic initiatives to overcome Italy's current limitations and capitalize on future growth opportunities. Enhancing carrier capacity, diversifying international routes, and upgrading airport infrastructure are pivotal steps toward securing Italy's place in the competitive landscape of global air cargo [17].

Technological innovations are helping bring needed improvements to supply chain efficiency, driven by market trends, including the growth of e-commerce and increasing demand for fast deliveries, which are also driving the evolution of air cargo services [52]. The growth in the transportation of high-value products is increasing the growth of the air cargo market, creating opportunities for industry players that can adapt to changing consumer preferences and market dynamics [52]. In addition, adopting new technologies and optimizing air cargo networks are essential to meet the evolving demands of global trade and supply chains [53]. In this context, the nature of Italian products, which are particularly suitable for air transport given their high value/weight ratio, can promote growth. Consequently, the growth of the incumbent Italian air carrier, along with projects to integrate with other European carriers, could drive Italy's expansion in this sector given that despite its problems, globalization plays a key role in shaping the future of the air cargo industry [54].

The industry faces critical challenges too. The main air cargo hub differs from the national carrier's hub: In addition, the national carrier's is characterized by few long-haul connections and the absence of a fleet dedicated exclusively to cargo. This is exacerbated by the geographic location of the national carrier's hub, which is not at the center of Italy's most economically productive area, making it less attractive for cargo activities. Furthermore, to increase competitiveness, it is essential to improve the efficiency of customs procedures, which have often been criticized for long customs clearance times compared with those of other countries. Improving the speed and cost of Italy's customs services could significantly accelerate the movement of goods and make Italy's air cargo system more internationally competitive.

This study offers some policy suggestions to increase the competitiveness of Italy's air cargo sector: (1) invest in sustainable technologies; (2) invest in modernizing air cargo infrastructure, including cargo handling facilities and intermodal connectivity, to improve operational efficiency and capacity [57]. Upgrading the infrastructure will enable smoother cargo flows and support the sector's growth; (3) Foster collaboration among stakeholders in the air cargo supply chain to improve resilience and competitiveness [58]. Joint ventures and partnerships can lead to better service offerings, increased cargo capacity, and an expanded route network; (4) support innovation in air cargo operations through funding and incentives for research and development [59]; and (5) ensure the coordination of air cargo

policies and broader transportation and environmental policies to achieve sustainable growth [60]. Policy alignment can help balance economic development with environmental considerations and promote efficient air cargo operations; (6) invest in training and workforce development to improve demand forecasting, service quality, and operational management within air cargo terminals [61]; (7) encourage market diversification and explore emerging opportunities in high-value product transportation to expand the market reach of Italy's air cargo sector [59]; and (8) adapt to changing market trends to stimulate growth and competitiveness. Guiding local development can support and be supported by air cargo-dependent industries [9]. By implementing these policy recommendations, policymakers can contribute to the growth and competitiveness of Italy's air cargo sector by ensuring resilience in the face of global challenges and market dynamics.

Conclusion

Strengthening global economic openness and domestic competitiveness is a prominent topic. Economic policy based on trade and competitiveness should be a priority for policymakers worldwide to boost productivity and growth, as well as harness new sources of economic development, international trade, and consequent stability.

From our study, a picture emerges of the dynamics that influence air cargo transport as it relates to our RQs. The market share of air cargo represents a small fraction of foreign trade by volume, but is significant in terms of the total value of goods traded. It was noted from the case study that the growth of the air cargo sector has slowed down due to the lack of a national carrier with adequate capacity for long-haul routes. A common feature of many markets is the high concentration of traffic in a few major airports, which poses logistical and distribution challenges. The evidence shows that centralization requires effective strategies to optimize cargo management and distribution at the national level. The experiences of various countries highlight the importance of developing more widespread infrastructure and increased operational capacity to improve the competitiveness of the air cargo sector.

In terms of strategic initiatives, the main challenge for the sector is the lack of an Italian carrier with adequate long-haul capacity located in an airport that is best suited to meet the needs of trade. The increased capacity of a domestic carrier, combined with strategies to increase international connections, could significantly improve the competitiveness of Italy's air cargo market.

To meet these challenges, it is crucial to adopt strategic policies aimed at strengthening Italy's air cargo industry, including diversifying the international routes served and improving modern airport infrastructure in economic centers. Such initiatives are crucial for boosting the sector's competitiveness.

Future research should monitor the evolving policy landscape and market dynamics, adapting strategies to foster growth and resilience in the face of global economic volatility. This will provide valuable insights for policymakers, ensuring that Italy's air cargo sector can contribute to the country's economic development.

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Annex. Air transport of goods by country. Quantities. Million tons

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Belgium	1.015	1.126	1.089	1.251	1.416	1.398	1.585	2.084	1.729	1.519
Germany	4.336	4.326	4.467	4.773	4.843	4.685	4.498	5.290	4.939	4.593
Spain	0.594	0.594	0.639	0.742	0.807	0.816	0.600	0.783	0.845	0.996
France	2.362	2.381	2.402	2.450	2.408	2.372	1.938	2.279	2.139	2.123
Italy	0.876	0.917	0.992	1.078	1.066	1.022	0.776	1.016	1.034	1.019
Luxembourg	0.707	0.737	0.801	0.893	0.895	0.853	0.905	1.088	0.969	0.794
Netherlands	1.727	1.712	1.832	1.865	1.840	1.704	1.591	1.808	1.553	1.416